

Spectral, Magnetic, Mössbauer and Chemotherapeutical Studies of Iron(III) Complexes with various New Derivatives of Isonicotinic Acid Hydrazide

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Manuscript received 9 June 1989, revised 19 June 1990, accepted 9 July 1990

A number of iron(III) complexes with new hydrazones of isonicotinic acid hydrazide (INH) have been synthesised having general formula $[\text{FeL}_2\text{Cl}_2]\text{Cl}$, $[\text{FeL}'_2]\text{Cl}$ and $[\text{FeL}''_2]\text{Cl}_3$, where L=bidentate ligands *N*-isonicotinamidobenzalaldimine (INH-BNZL), *N*-isonicotinamidoanisalaldimine (INH-ANSL), *N*-isonicotinamido-3,4-dimethoxybenzalaldimine (INH-VAL), *N*-isonicotinamidobenzophenonimine (INH-BNZP), *N*-isonicotinamidocyclohexanonimine (INH-CYCLN), *N*-isonicotinamidobenzylacetoneimine (INH-BNZLA), *N*-isonicotinamido-*p*-dimethylaminobenzalaldimine (INH-PDAB), *N*-isonicotinamido-*p*-dimethylaminocinnamalaldimine (INH-PDMCD) and *N*-isonicotinamido-3-methoxy-4-hydroxybenzalaldimine (INH-VAN); and tridentate ligands L'=*N*-isonicotinamidosalicylalaldimine (INH-HSAL) and L''=*N*-isonicotinamidofurfuralaldimine (INH-FURAL), and characterised by elemental analysis, magnetic susceptibility, electronic, infrared and Mossbauer spectral measurements, revealing high-spin octahedral stereochemistry of these complexes. They have also been screened for antitubercular and antibacterial activities against *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* and gram-positive and gram-negative organisms

STUDIES on *d*-metal complexes of biologically active substituted heterocyclic compounds have recently attracted considerable attention¹. The present paper deals with the synthesis and characterisation of iron(III) complexes with recently synthesised² chemotherapeutically active derivatives of isonicotinic acid hydrazide (INH). The results are discussed with the aid of spectral, magnetic, Mössbauer, infrared and chemotherapeutical data.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were B.D.H. reagents or of equivalent grade. Ligands were synthesised by condensing isonicotinic acid hydrazide (INH) with various aldehydes and ketones and recrystallised from ethanol (95%).

Preparation of complexes: All the iron(III) complexes with various INH-derivatives (hydrazones) were prepared by the following method. The methanolic solutions of aldehydic/ketonic hydrazone of isonicotinic acid hydrazide (INH) and of anhydrous iron(III) chloride (metal salt in excess) were slowly mixed by following the stoichiometry M:L=1:2 and refluxed for ~2 h. The mixture was then concentrated, cooled and the resulting solid was washed with methanol, benzene and solvent ether, and recrystallised from ethanol (95%) and dried under vacuum over fused calcium

chloride. The estimation of metal content was carried out on a Perkin-Elmer 2380 atomic absorption spectrometer. Carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen were determined microanalytically and the chloride gravimetrically as silver chloride.

The ir (KBr) and far-ir (nujol) spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer 1320 and Beckman IR-5A spectrophotometers respectively, and the reflectance spectra on a Unicam SP-700 spectrophotometer using MgO as the reference. Magnetic susceptibility measurements were carried out on a Princeton Applied Research 155 vibrating sample magnetometer. Mossbauer spectra were recorded on a ND-1100 Multichannel Analyser (MCA) spectrometer. A constant acceleration mode was applied and data were recorded in 512 channels. A ⁶⁷Co source was used in Pd-matrix. The velocity was calibrated using Na₂[Fe(CN)₅NO]·2H₂O (SNP) standard and the centroid of the two peaks of SNP was assumed as zero. The isomer shifts were converted into natural α-Fe standard using the equation, $IS_{\text{Fe}} = IS_{\text{SNP}} - 0.26$ (mm s⁻¹). The error limits for the Mossbauer parameters were less than or equal to 0.02 mm s⁻¹. The spectrum was fitted to Lorentzian curves by the least-squares method.

The *in vitro* antitubercular activity of the complexes was studied against *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* at 0.2, 0.4, 1, 5 and 10 μg ml⁻¹ (solvent, DMSO) against H₃₇R_v strain of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* using Lowenstein-Jensen egg medium.

The retardation of growth rate was studied upto 6 weeks at 37°. The procedure was duplicated using only solvent for control purpose. The antibacterial activities were studied against gram-positive (*S. aureus*, *B. subtilis*, *B. pumilis*) and gram-negative (*K. pneumoniae*, *E. coli*) organisms by following the usual cup-plate-agar diffusion method using nutrient agar medium. Fresh solutions of all the compounds and the control were prepared in dimethylsulphoxide (DMSO). The tests were run in triplicate and the average of the inhibition zones noted.

Results and Discussion

Analytical data (Table 1) indicate that the complexes have the composition $[\text{FeL}_2\text{Cl}_2]\text{Cl}$, $[\text{FeL}_2]\text{Cl}$ and $[\text{FeL}'_2]\text{Cl}_3$. Some complexes melt at 122–152° and the others decompose at 220–265°. The complexes are freely soluble in methanol and ethanol and highly soluble in DMF and DMSO.

The magnetic susceptibility values (Table 1) of all of the complexes at room temperature (300 ± 1 K) observed in the range 5.13–6.07 B.M., are in close agreement to the spin-only value of 5.92 B.M., which ascertain high-spin octahedral stereochemistry of the proposed ligands around iron(III) ion.

The electronic spectra of the ligands show two to three bands in the region 240–300 nm, which are assigned to the $\pi \dots \pi^*$ transitions. The ligand band occurring at 370 nm (*N*-isonicotinamidosalicylaldehyde) shifts to the longer wavelength on complex formation and appears at 410 nm. Such a large shift may be ascribed to strong metal-ligand bonding. In addition, the bands in this region may have contribution from ligand-metal charge transfer transitions as well, thus resulting in yellow to brick red, red-brown and dark brown colours

of the complexes. The brownish red colour of the complexes is ascribed to the presence of one or more low lying charge transfer absorption bands³ in the near-infrared region which may be assigned to ligand field charge transfers. In the iron(III) complexes, the bands observed at 13 005–13 710, 16 000–17 640 and 26 600–27 655 cm^{-1} are tentatively assigned⁴ to ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(G)$, ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(G)$ and ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4E_g(G)$ transitions. The calculated values of $10Dq$, Racah interelectronic repulsion parameters (B_{33} , C), nephelauxetic ratio (β_{33}), Condon-Shortley repulsion parameters (F_2 , F_4) and L. F. S. E. (data summarised in Table 2) for the iron(III) complexes are found in good agreement to the previous reports for high-spin octahedral stereochemistry around iron(III) ion.

From Mössbauer spectra of the iron(III) complexes with INH-derivatives, the value of isomer shift ($\delta^{I.S.}$) and quadrupole splitting (ΔE_q) are found in the range 0.517–0.617 mm s^{-1} and 0.657–0.877 mm s^{-1} respectively at 301 K. These data ascertain⁵ high-spin or weak ligand field octahedral microsymmetry of the ligands around the Mossbauer atom and these observations are also in good agreement to the earlier reports^{6,7}. A decrease in isomer shift may be presumed⁸ due to slight increase in the electron density on the oxygen and nitrogen donor atoms in the ligands, which in turn should result in a greater σ -overlap and hence an increased electron density on the iron nucleus is expected. In other words, the lower values of $\delta^{I.S.}$ in the high-spin iron(III) octahedral complexes may also be attributed to a decrease in the 4s-electron density on the iron nucleus due to the decreased covalency of donor metal bonds⁶.

A study and comparison of the ir spectra of the ligands and the complexes, imply that all the

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Sl. no.	Compd.*	Colour	M.p. °C	Analysis % · Found/(Calcd.)			μ_{eff} B.M.
				M	N	Cl	
1.	$[\text{Fe}(\text{INH-BNZI})_2\text{Cl}_2]\text{Cl}$	Dark yellow	225 ^a	8.67 (9.11)	12.83 (13.71)	18.22 (17.36)	5.94
2.	$[\text{Fe}(\text{INH-ANSL})_2\text{Cl}_2]\text{Cl}$	Orangish yellow	220 ^a	8.95 (8.30)	11.67 (12.49)	16.62 (15.51)	5.13
3.	$[\text{Fe}(\text{INH-VAL})_2\text{Cl}_2]\text{Cl}$	Dark yellow	125	7.81 (7.62)	12.72 (11.47)	13.22 (14.51)	5.82
4.	$[\text{Fe}(\text{INH-BNZP})_2\text{Cl}_2]\text{Cl}$	Blackish brown	122	8.01 (7.30)	10.57 (10.99)	11.97 (13.90)	5.92
5.	$[\text{Fe}(\text{INH-CYCLN})_2\text{Cl}_2]\text{Cl}$	Blackish brown	128	10.02 (9.36)	13.21 (14.08)	18.76 (17.92)	5.86
6.	$[\text{Fe}(\text{INH-BNZLA})_2\text{Cl}_2]\text{Cl}$	Blackish brown	131	7.98 (8.01)	11.13 (12.06)	16.83 (15.26)	5.87
7.	$[\text{Fe}(\text{INH-PDAB})_2\text{Cl}_2]\text{Cl}$	Chocolate	230 ^a	8.21 (7.99)	14.92 (16.04)	14.81 (15.22)	6.03
8.	$[\text{Fe}(\text{INH-PDMCD})_2\text{Cl}_2]\text{Cl}$	Chocolate	240 ^a	7.11 (7.44)	15.71 (14.92)	13.63 (14.16)	5.86
9.	$[\text{Fe}(\text{INH-VAN})_2\text{Cl}_2]\text{Cl}$	Greenish brown	265 ^a	8.20 (7.92)	10.55 (11.92)	14.11 (15.09)	5.88
10.	$[\text{Fe}(\text{INH-SAL})_2]\text{Cl}$	Chocolate	152	9.45 (9.73)	12.97 (14.64)	6.01 (6.18)	6.07
11.	$[\text{Fe}(\text{INH-FURAI})_2]\text{Cl}_3$	Dark green	235 ^a	9.07 (9.42)	12.66 (14.18)	18.79 (17.95)	5.73

*Decomposition point.

TABLE 2—ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA AND RELEVANT LIGAND FIELD ENERGY PARAMETERS

Sl. no.*	Observed λ_{max} (cm ⁻¹) ^a A _{1g} → ^a T _{1g} (G)	10Dq cm ⁻¹	B ₃₃ cm ⁻¹	β_{33}	F ₂ K.K.	F ₄ K.K.	L.F.S.E. kcal mol ⁻¹
1.	13 350	13 350	1 213.6	0.93	93.45	61.17	8.48
2.	13 100	13 100	1 190.9	0.91	91.70	60.02	8.32
3.	13 550	13 550	1 231.8	0.95	94.85	62.02	8.60
4.	13 200	13 200	1 200.0	0.92	92.40	60.48	8.40
5.	13 370	13 370	1 215.5	0.93	93.59	61.26	8.49
6.	13 410	13 410	1 219.1	0.94	93.87	61.44	8.52
7.	13 650	13 650	1 240.9	0.95	95.55	62.54	8.67
8.	13 710	13 710	1 246.4	0.96	95.97	62.82	8.71
9.	13 050	13 050	1 186.4	0.91	91.35	59.79	8.29
10.	13 610	13 610	1 237.3	0.95	95.27	62.36	8.64
11.	13 240	13 240	1 203.6	0.92	92.63	60.66	8.41

*Corresponds to the complexes in Table 1.

ligands are bidentate with carbonyl oxygen and azomethine nitrogen as two coordination sites except *N*-isonicotinamidosalicylalimine and *N*-isonicotinamidofurfuralaldimine, which are found tridentate having three coordination sites, viz. carbonyl-O, azomethine-N and phenolic-O and carbonyl-O, azomethine-N and heterocyclic-O respectively. The sharp absorption bands in the ir spectra of free ligands, appearing at 1 610–1 680 cm⁻¹ (C=O amide band I) are shifted to lower frequencies by 40–60 cm⁻¹, which clearly indicates carbonyl oxygen-metal bond. It is also supported by blue-shifts observed in amide band III and IV, clearly indicating the involvement of C=O group in coordination. This $\nu_{C=O}$ band can be correlated to the stretching vibration mode of the conjugate >C=N–N=C< moiety. Such behaviour is diagnostic of the enolisation of the hydrazone residue. The enolisation of the ligand is further confirmed by a new strong band at 1 515–1 505 cm⁻¹ (NCO)⁹. The $\nu_{C=N}$ mode, appearing in the ligands at 1 585–1 635 cm⁻¹ is lowered by about 20–30 cm⁻¹ in the spectra of corresponding iron(III) chelates, suggesting¹⁰ that the coordination occurs through nitrogen of the azomethine group^{11,12}. The strong bands observed at 1 520–1 575 and 1 000–1 080 cm⁻¹ are tentatively assigned¹³ to antisymmetric and symmetric $\nu_{C=O} + \nu_{C=N}$ of pyridine ring and pyridine ring breathings, and deformations remains practically unchanged in frequency and band intensities revealing non-involvement of pyridinic nitrogen and metal bond. However, the assignment¹⁴ is not unambiguous because N–N group of the liquid also absorbs in this region 890–1 000 cm⁻¹. The spectra of the present complexes donot show absorptions attributable to ν_{OH} , ν_{NH} and $\nu_{C=O}$ modes, indicating thereby the change from ketonic form to the enolic form of the ligand during complexation¹⁵ and deprotonation of OH/NH group.

The far-ir spectral bands in the ligands are practically unchanged in the complexes. But some new bands with medium to weak intensities appear in the regions 484–455, 342–320 and 285–270 cm⁻¹ in the complexes under study, which are tentatively assigned to $\nu_{Fe-azomethine-N}$, $\nu_{Fe-enolic-O}$ and $\nu_{Fe-chlorine}$ respectively, and are in accordance to the previous reports^{11,16}.

Therefore, the studies reveal high-spin octahedral stereochemistry around iron(III) ion as shown in structure 1.

1

[FeL₂Cl₂]Cl; X=Cl
[FeL'₂]Cl; X=O (phenolic)
[FeL''₂]Cl₃; X=O (thiophen)

Biological studies: All the complexes were screened for their antitubercular as well as anti-bacterial activities *in vitro*. The complexes showed both the activities. In case of antitubercular study of the compounds, minimum inhibitory concentration (mic) was found about 1 μ g ml⁻¹. However, the complexes having functional groups like OH, OCH₃, N(CH₃)₂ and CH=CH showed higher activity than the others (mic, about 0.2 μ g ml⁻¹). The complexes were also found active against both types organisms, and were significantly active against *S. aureus* and *E. coli*.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Head, Department of Physics and Astrophysics, University of Delhi, to Director, U. S. I. C., Roorkee University, and to Prof. (Mrs.) S. Chandrashekar, Microbiology Department, Patel Chest House, Delhi, for their kind assistance.

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